

RECYCLING AND MANAGEMENT OF EXTINGUISHING WATER

Nguyen Huu Dung

Faculty of Fire Engineering and Technology

University of fire prevention and fighting

243 Khuat Duy Tien, Thanh Xuan, 1000, Ha Noi, Viet Nam

Abstract

During firefighting, water will accumulate without evaporation and become heavily contaminated. Contaminated water after firefighting can harm water sources or seep into the soil, even contaminating groundwater sources. Therefore, contaminated water after firefighting should not be discharged into the environment without control of harmful components to the water source and natural environment. Scientific management and recycling of firefighting water helps reduce the amount of water used during firefighting and protects the environment from pollution.

1. Introduction

The use of fresh water (especially potable water) is costly to society. Large fires can require several million liters of water. For example, the fire at Allied Colloids (Bradford, England) in 1992 consumed about 16 million liters of water. Depending on the drinking water supply charging regime, water bills can easily run into several hundred thousand pounds. Therefore, it is necessary to estimate the amount of firefighting water to reduce costs and harm to the receiving environment. The amount of firefighting water discharged into any drainage system or tank is complex to assess, because modeling and standardizing the effective duration of a fire and the associated water consumption requires needed to extinguish a fire depends on many variables[1-4]. Appropriate assumptions must be made regarding the amount of flammable and/or combustible material. Furthermore, fire rate, evaporation effects, available fire suppression systems and process isolation devices must also be considered. Estimating the duration of a fire situation will lead to an assessment of actual firefighting water consumption. The results can be used to estimate the size of the fire drainage system and the capacity of the fire water storage tanks. Within the scope of hazard and risk analysis, it is necessary to first identify all issues related to the potential for contamination of extinguishing water after a fire [5-9]. For

combustion products, it is used to evaluate quality. Here, it should be considered that a fire can cause the production of substances that lead to further extinguishing with water

2. Fire Water Management

2.1. Estimate the amount of contaminated water after firefighting

The amount of contaminated water after firefighting depends on many factors, including the type and composition of the fire, the duration of the fire, the development of the fire, the firefighting plan of the fire protection unit, as well as the local infrastructure. convenient for fire prevention. Therefore, as expressed in the current guidelines, the problems of endangering water supplies by harmful substances and the potential for development of harmful substances in fires are used as criteria for the Safety requirements relate to the scale of fire prevention measures and are the basis for assessing the need to implement post-fire water collection measures. The amount of firefighting water stated in the range of fires in medium-sized industrial facilities ranges from 3,200 to 14,000 liters/minute. In such fires, there is about 192 m³ to 840 m³ of firefighting water per hour and usually extinguishes the fire for a period of 2 to 4 hours.

Fig.1. Contaminated water after firefighting

About half of that water will evaporate. Estimated amount of contaminated post-fire fighting water is determined through the formula below: The relevant parameters are explained as follows.

$$V = \{ (A_{act} * SWL * BAF * BBF) + M \} / BSF$$

To make application easier, we have made a calculation sheet attached to these instructions.

2.2. Recycle fire water

Treatment and circulation of firefighting water to firefighting training facilities to achieve water quality

suitable for the purpose has been recommended. Options with and without fire water recirculation are being developed to upgrade and refurbish fire water supply systems to remove contaminants to the greatest extent possible and address the criteria based on risk such as limiting negative impacts on the natural environment and the health of firefighters. For larger facilities, on-site wastewater treatment facilities appropriately sized to allow collection and subsequent treatment of contaminated firefighting water are a viable option. However, no direct reference is made to any specific treatment technology that may be suitable.

Fig.2. Recycle fire water

The Irish Environmental Protection Agency does not generally recommend the use of fire water ponds as a source of fire water for continued use when fighting fires. The primary reason for this recommendation is the lack of information collected on contaminants in firefighting water streams, suggesting a need for a review of the literature and further research. Information on entrained products such as water reactivity, corrosivity and toxicity must be available before recycling. Exceptions may be allowed for fire emergencies on a case-by-case basis[10-18].

2.3. Collect fire fighting water

To collect water after firefighting, it is necessary to have a self-operating structural system that is permanently installed without leakage and provides the necessary volume:

◆ Fire water collection tanks are built for this purpose and are connected to the building without the need for a pump. Areas with special hazards (e.g. electroplating equipment, chemical storage facilities) must be installed directly in sufficiently large separators.

◆ Final inspection wells in the post-fire water collection area should be of fireproof construction (do not use synthetic fiber materials).

◆ Avoid using indoor rainwater pipes in areas that collect water after firefighting. Where necessary, these pipes must be designed to be fire resistant, with a height as low as the intended flow blocking height (e.g. poured into concrete).

◆ Construct floors of buildings that act as water gathering places (berms, sills, slopes, and interceptors); And according to the law on liquid storage, this place also needs to be large enough to collect enough firefighting water when a fire occurs.

◆ Build existing underground water reservoirs or basements to store contaminated firefighting water.

◆ Sufficiently large wastewater treatment plant storage tanks and/or rainwater tanks.

Fig.3. Facility for retention of extinguishing water in the basement under the building

2.4. Prevent firefighting water from entering the drain

If firefighting water flows into surface drains, it can have devastating effects on aquatic life. Firefighters carry environmental containment equipment including manhole covers to prevent firefighting water from entering the drain. But if an appropriate containment zone

Fig.4. Estate polluted by foam-based firewater runoff

3. Results and Discussion

The opportunity to recycle firefighting water should be balanced by considering alternative options to achieve the same goal. For major fire incidents and if economically justified, fire extinguishing water should be pre-treated before recycling with the aid of filtration devices, which promotes the recycling of fire extinguishing water without danger. This can minimize health problems associated with contaminants coming into contact with the skin and/or entering the nose, mouth and eyes of firefighters and the general public during live fire incidents. A much simpler filter based on sieving and filtration technology can be used to prevent large particles from clogging the pump. However, these filters must be relatively small due to space constraints in the container. Additionally, a false bottom in a temporary fire water tank can separate large solids from the fire water by gravity, reducing the risk of them being sucked into the pump where they can cause blockages.

In the unavoidable event of spillage of firefighting water heavily contaminated with solids and grit into the sewer system, prompt cleaning of sludge traps is possible in coordination with the sewer operator (United Utilities) and the Environment Agency as a preventative measure to protect the environment from avoidable pollution. However, there will need to be a corresponding cultural change within the fire service, which focuses on firefighting rather than protecting the environment. However, silt trap management can be integrated in the proposed decision support tool that includes aspects such as management and technological solutions for different problem situations.

4. Conclusions

The author recommends that applied research be conducted on rapid on-site storage and disposal options for fire extinguishing water and foam. It is necessary to research portable filtration devices that capture large particles with lightweight plastic materials and dissolved pollutants with activated carbon. Considering that fire water flow rates can be high, further study of

hydraulic performance including design flow rate and empty bed contact time of the treatment system should also be performed.

References

1. Department of Environment and Conservation. Environmental Compliance Report: Liquid Chemical Storage, Handling and Spill Management (Part A: Compliance Audit); Department of Environment and Conservation: New South Wales, Sydney, Australia, 1995.
2. Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG). Environment Handbook for the Fire and Rescue Service. National Operational Guidance Programme Consultation Document; DCLG and the Environment Agency: London, UK, 2013.
3. Risk and Policy Analysts (RPA). Risk Reduction Strategy and Analysis of Advantages and Drawbacks for Perfluorooctane Sulphonate (PFOS); Final Report Prepared by RPA for the Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs and the Environment Agency for England and Wales in association with the British Research Establishment Environment. Norfolk, England, UK, 2004.
4. Country Fire Authority (CFA). Response to the Professor Joy Report of the independent investigation into the CFA Facility at Fiskville. CFA: Burwood East, Victoria, Australia.
5. Vince, I. Major Accidents to the Environment—A Practical Guide to the Seveso II-Directive and COMAH Regulations; Butterworth-Heinemann, Elsevier: Oxford, UK, 2008. [Google Scholar]
6. Rigolio, M. Fire Fighting in Process Plants: Analysis of Actual Firewater Consumption. In Proceedings of the CISAP4, 4th International Conference on Safety and Environment in Process Industry, Florence, Italy, 14–17 March 2010.
7. Rodante, T.V. Investigation of a naphtha storage tank fire. Process Saf. Progress 2005, 24, 98–107.

8. Environment Agency. Containment of Bulk Hazardous Liquids at COMAH Establishments—Containment Policy Supporting Guidance for Secondary and Tertiary Containment; Environment Agency, Health and Safety Executive and Scottish Environment Protection Agency: London and Stirling, UK, 2008.
9. Health and Safety Executive (HSE). Safety and Environmental Standards for Fuel Storage Sites; Final Report. Process Safety Leadership Group, HSE: London, UK, 2009.
10. Environmental Protection Agency. Fire-water Retention Facilities: (Draft) Guidance Note to Industry on the Requirements for Fire-water Retention Facilities; Environmental Protection Agency: Wexford, Ireland.
11. Eke, P.E.; Scholz, M. Benzene removal with vertical-flow constructed treatment wetlands. *J. Chem. Technol. Biotechnol.* 2008, 83, 55–63.
12. Whitfield, A.; Nicholas, M. Bunding at Buncefield: Successes, Failures and Lessons Learned. *Hazards XX: Process Safety and Environmental Protection: Harnessing Knowledge—Challenging Competency*. In Institution of Chemical Engineers Symposium Series; Institution of Chemical Engineers: Rugby, UK, 2008. [Google Scholar]
13. Buncefield firewater clean-up under way. *In Professional Engineering*; 2006; p. 12.
14. Rivers, K. Safety and Environmental Standards for Fuel Storage Sites.
15. Back, B.M. *Environmental Innovations: An Introduction*.
16. Ramirez, P.A.P.; Johnsen, R.; Utne, I.B. Probabilistic Condition Assessment of Aging Equipment Considering the Effect of Operating Conditions and Maintenance. In *Proceedings of the 31st American Society of Mechanical Engineers International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering*, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, 1–6 July 2012; Volume 2, pp. 535–545.
17. Greater Manchester Fire and Rescue Services (GMFRS). *Environmental Protection Strategy*; GMFRS: Salford, UK, 2009.
18. Scholz, M. *Wetland Systems to Control Urban Runoff*; Elsevier: Amsterdam, the Netherlands, 2006.